

Swiss Reproducibility Network (SwissRN)

Annual Report 2025

Swiss Reproducibility Network (SwissRN)
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¹ See <https://www.swissrn.org/contents/community/organisation/> for more details.

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Piera Filippi collected input from the authors, namely the SwissRN working groups and local nodes' leads , and compiled it into this booklet, which was subsequently reviewed and copy-edited by Daniel Stekhoven and Francesco Santini.

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General Introduction

The Swiss Reproducibility Network (SwissRN) is currently funded by the SNSF to cover coordination and communication costs. Each local node supports the network by promoting activities that advance transparent, robust, and reproducible research practices, in line with the SwissRN strategy.

The present **Annual Report 2025** presents an overview of the network's activities and developments over the past year. The report documents the progress made by SwissRN in promoting rigorous, transparent, and reproducible (RTR) research across Switzerland, through the coordinated efforts of its working groups (including the SwissRN Academy) and its local nodes.

The annual report is based on the outcomes and discussions of the **SwissRN 4th Annual Meeting**, capturing the key presentations, insights, and initiatives shared during the event. It reports and reflects the contributions of local nodes, working groups, and international RN representatives, highlighting both ongoing activities and areas for improvement. By documenting the exchanges made during the meeting, the report provides a comprehensive overview of the network's progress.

During 2025, SwissRN continued to consolidate its role as a national platform connecting researchers, institutions, and stakeholders committed to improving research quality and integrity. The network supported initiatives aimed at advancing open science and responsible research practices, including working groups' activities related to open research data, preregistration and registered reports, computational reproducibility, responsible research assessment, and training in good research practices. These initiatives were complemented by a range of community-building activities such as workshops, seminars, hackathons, and discussion events designed to facilitate knowledge exchange and capacity building within the research community.

The report highlights the contributions of SwissRN's local nodes, which play a key role in implementing and promoting reproducibility-related initiatives within their respective institutions. Through local events, educational activities, and collaborative projects, these nodes contribute to strengthening awareness of reproducibility challenges and to embedding open and transparent research practices across the Swiss research landscape.

Together, the activities described in this report illustrate SwissRN's continued commitment to fostering a coordinated national effort toward improving research practices and supporting the long-term development of an RTR research culture in Switzerland.

The report is structured in four parts. The first part presents the outcomes (e.g., activities, workshops, and publications) and areas for improvement of the working groups. The second part focuses on the outcomes and areas for improvement of each local node. The third part focuses on SwissRN's key network milestone in 2025 and the sources of funding that were secured to further support its activities. Finally, the fourth part concludes the report and glimpses at the coming year.

1. Working groups: Report on Activities 2025

Open Research Data (ORD)

Lead: Gorka Fraga González

One of the main achievements of the ORD working group has been enhancing the communication of ORD-related activities. This was accomplished by launching a blog, which has published 24 entries since 2024.

Key outcomes:

- Several posts have been used to inform key stakeholders about specific projects.
- Three new members joined the working group.

Areas for improvement:

- The blog is active but would benefit from more consistent contributions.
- Despite three new members joining in 2025, UZH continues to be the primary contributor.

Preregistration and Registered Reports

Lead: Evie Vergauwe and Hanno Würbel

Project: Strengthening the Interoperability and Reusability of Research Outputs

Activities were conducted within the framework of the project “Strengthen the Interoperability and Reusability of Research Outputs,” funded by Swissuniversities and the Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (FSVO), led by Dr. Cristina Priboi.

Key outcomes:

- Conducted a survey on preregistration among Swiss-based animal researchers (Priboi et al., submitted).
- Conducted interviews on preregistration with Swiss-based animal researchers (Priboi et al., submitted).
- Organized a roundtable event with multiple stakeholders to discuss strategies for implementing preregistration in animal research.

Areas for improvement:

None reported.

Computational Reproducibility

Lead: Daniel Stekhoven and Matthias Voigt

The purpose of the computational reproducibility WG is to bring together researchers from diverse fields to foster community connections and facilitate open discussions on individual practices in computational reproducibility. The group aims to share ideas and collaboratively identify best practices that are applicable across topics and disciplines. By establishing these standards, the working group seeks to publish best practice guidelines and ultimately develop an educational course to support the broader research community.

Key outcomes:

- Computational Reproducibility Hackathon in Brig
- Online Seminar Series
- Submitted a publication about the Hackathon on F1000Research (Title: “Insights from the SwissRN Computational Reproducibility Hackaton 2025)

Figure 1. Computational Reproducibility Hackathon (Brig) — event photo.

Areas for improvement:

- Managing demanding schedules effectively
- Implementing structured workflows

Research Assessment and Incentives

Lead: Rachel Heyard

Over the past two years, this working group has focused on advancing responsible research evaluation and fostering collaboration across institutions. Its activities have included participating in key initiatives on research metrics and data evaluation, as well as organizing discussions to reinvigorate and expand the group's work.

Key outcomes:

- 2024 and 2025: represented SwissRN within CoARA WG on Responsible Metrics and indicators
- 2025:
 - Represented SwissRN within “Implementing Data Evaluation in Academia” Working Group (<https://zenodo.org/records/17293504>)
 - Conducted brainstorming meetings to re-ignite the working group

Areas for improvement:

- Increase the number of active members
- Find a common focus for the group to work

ReproducibiliTEA

Leads: Rachel Heyard, Claudia Weidensteiner and Evie Vergauwe

ReproducibiliTEA is a researcher-led initiative that supports the formation of local journal clubs dedicated to open science, research reproducibility, and improving research practices.

Key outcome:

- Organized monthly online and hybrid events (open science games (UNIGE), or talks followed by Q&A (UZH, UNIBAS, UNIGE) - Attendance: up to around 20 participants)

Areas for improvement:

- Expand the number of joint sessions across SwissRN local nodes

UZH ReproducibiliTea
 Schedule Spring 2025
 On Thursday from 16:30 to 17:15
 20. February
 A Supervised Machine Learning Approach for Assessing Grant Peer Review Reports (DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.2411.16662) with **Gabriel Okasa**, Swiss National Science Foundation
 6. March
 Trust in Scientists and their Role in Society: A 68-Country Survey (DOI: 10.1038/s41562-024-02090-5) with **Nais Mede & Viktoria Cologna**, University of Zurich and Collegium Helveticum
 20. March
 Intersections between Reproducibility and Diversity with **Stephanie Zellers**, University of Helsinki
 3. April
 What is a high quality pre-registration? (DOI: 10.31219/osf.io/wc7qr) with **Lena Hahn**, Trier University
 24. April
 Where are my data? The AFFORD workflow to create your own data index with Git, R and Quarto (DOI: 10.31222/osf.io/64fch) with **Gorka Fraga Gonzalez**, University of Zurich
 8. May
 Scholars' Perception of Reproducibility Across Disciplines in the Context of Research Assessment with **Michael Ochsner**, FORS
 22. May
 Catching the wave: Language models accelerate evidence management with **Janna Hastings**, University of Zurich
 Registration and further information on <https://www.crs.uzh.ch/en/training/ReproducibiliTea.html>

ReproducibiliTea Journal Club Geneva
 Autumn Meetings at Uni Mail and via Zoom

Date	Title	Description
Friday 31.10. 16h-17h @ Uni Mail 3141	Trick or Treat: Open Science Edition Open Science Boardgame	An easy-going introductory boardgame, ideal to learn about Open Science practices
Friday 21.11. 16h-17h @ Uni Mail 3141 and on Zoom	The use of artificial intelligence in open science: opportunities, limitations, and ethical considerations.	Hybrid Format: Presentation by Dr. Maria Cappelli and Prof. Giovanna di Marzo Serugendo and discussion on challenges at the intersection of artificial intelligence and open science
Friday 12.12. 16h-17h @ Uni Mail 3141 and on Zoom	Do I Really Need to Preregister? - An introduction to Preregistration	An introductory session on preregistration, focusing on common doubts and insecurities around the topic

Contact us for more info or the Zoom access: reproducibiliTea@unige.ch

ReproducibiliTea UniBasel 2025

Date	Topic	Presenter
25.09.25	Post-publication reviewing and commenting	Paulina Manduch
18.10.25	Increasing computational reproducibility or how-to share "you" research code	Camille Maumet
06.11.25	Advancing automated assessment of research findings.	Andrew Tyrer
20.11.25	Research on research at the SNSF Towards best practices in research funding	Matthias Egger
04.12.25	Taboo topics we can no longer avoid: Negligence, tampering, and fraud	Ian Hussey
18.12.25	Claims about scientific rigour require rigour Joint Session RT Switzerland	Berna Devezter

On Thursdays from 15:30-16:30 (CET)

Figures 2. ReproducibiliTEA outreach efforts (promotional materials and snapshots from online events).

Training

Lead: Fabio Molo

This working group successfully secured a **swissuniversities project grant**, a collaboration between FernUni, UZH (CRS) and HES-SO, aimed at improving accessibility and openness of educational resources in Open Science. The project focuses on developing a centralized catalogue and transforming existing materials from CRS “Good Research Practice” courses into **Open Educational Resources (OER)**.

Key outcomes:

- Received grant from swissuniversities project with FernUni and HES-SO
- Working on an Open Science Education Catalogue ([Link](#))
- Made existing educational resources “open” (OER)

Areas for improvement:

None reported. New members for the working group are welcome.

Open Science Education Catalogue

A collection of educational resources on Open Science

Version 0.1

AUTHORS

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MODIFIED

November 24, 2025

This site collects courses and educational materials that teach open and reproducible research practices, with a focus on resources from Swiss higher education institutions.

The screenshot shows the Open Science Education Catalogue interface. It features a navigation bar with 'Important', 'Topics', and 'Important exchange platforms for educational resources'. Below this, there are filters for 'Filter by Topic:' (with 'Computational Reproducibility' selected) and 'Filter by Language:' (with 'de', 'en', and 'fr' options). A 'CSV' button and a search box are also present. The main content is a table with columns for Name, Institution, Description, Mode, Access, and URL.

Name	Institution	Description	Mode	Access	URL
ARIS Institutional Repository (SUPSI)	SUPSI	SUPSI repository for publications and projects	async	public	https://aris.supsi.ch/home
Columbia University Reproducibility Guidelines	Columbia University	NIH-focused reproducibility resources	async	public	https://research.columbia.edu/reproducibility-reso...
EPFL Docker in Research	EPFL	Docker for reproducible research	async	public	https://c4dt.epfl.ch/article/docker-in-research-de...
FAIR Data, Better Science	International	Discussion on connected labs and FAIR data practices	async	public	https://www.scisure.com/blog/fair-data-better-scie...
Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT)		Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training advancing research transparency, reproducibility, rigor, and public benefit		public	https://forrt.org/

Figure 3. Open Science Education Catalogue — screenshot.

SwissRN Academy

Lead: Samuel Pawel

The SwissRN Academy has continued to grow and actively engaged its community. Membership has increased, and activities, such as skill-building workshops and networking events, have helped to strengthen connections among junior researchers interested in reproducibility across Switzerland. After nearly four years in the role, Samuel Pawel has stepped down as coordinator of the SwissRN Academy, and three new co-leaders have been appointed: Johanna Einsiedler (Basel), Noémie Kuenzi (Geneva), Luisa Jansen (Bern).

Key outcomes:

- Gained new members (+18 since last annual meeting)
- 15 May – Workshop: Reproducible and Dynamic Reporting with R and Quarto in Zurich
- 11 September – Early Career Reviewer Workshop in Bern
- 14 November – Workshop: Reproducible Research Workflows with Quarto and R in Geneva
- 05 December – Social Meetup at the SwissRN Annual Meeting in Basel

Areas for improvement:

- Increase the number of active members
- Assemble members from different universities in the same physical location

Figure 4. ECR peer review workshop in Bern.

Figure 5. Reproducible research workflows workshop in Geneva.

2. Local Nodes: Report on activities 2025

Below a list of activities by which each local node strengthened its role in advancing open and reproducible science in 2025:

CERN

Local Node representative: Tibor Simko

March 2025:

- Hosted Snakemake Hackathon 2025. ([event](#))
- Was selected to take part in the European Open Science Cloud Federation build-up phase. ([web](#))

Figure 6. CERN activity highlight — picture & screenshot (March 2025).

August 2025:

- As part of the International Committee for Future Accelerators panel on Data Lifecycle published recommendations for best practices for data preservation and open science. ([PDF](#))
- Offered a holistic point of view from researchers to laboratory management to policy makers within the *HEP best practices – open science* project

Figure 7. Best practice paper on arXiv and HEP tool to filter recommendations.

September 2025:

- Published its first ever Open Science Report. ([PDF](#))
- Hosted the Open Science Fair. ([event](#))

Figure 8. Participants at the Open Science Fair at CERN.

Link to slides:

- [T. Simko, On the importance of computational reproducibility in fostering Open and FAIR Science](#)
- [C. Lange, Nudging Scientists into adopting Open Science Practices](#)

November 2025:

- Organized a School on IT Services including reproducibility lesson. ([event](#))

- A federated REANA Snakemake workflow execution example ran on several EOSC Nodes presented at the EOSC Symposium. ([slides and video](#))

EPFL – Lausanne

Local Node representative: Michael Herzog

Offered the module “Understanding Statistics and Experimental Design” (BIO-449, 4 credits), taught by Michael Herzog in English. This course is designed not as an introduction to the mathematics behind statistics or to statistical software like R, but rather to deepen students’ understanding of statistics through the lens of experimental design. The module aims to help participants avoid common pitfalls in statistical reasoning and provides opportunities to discuss ongoing research projects. Key topics covered include sensitivity and bias, statistical power, Bayes theorem and odds ratio, the interpretation of t-tests, classical statistical tests, principles of experimental design, and issues related to fraud and misconduct in statistics. Assessment is conducted via a written exam.

FernUNI Schweiz

Local Node representatives: Michael Kurschilgen, Matthias Voigt

June 2025:

- Organized the Computational Reproducibility Hackathon (June 6, Brig)

Figure 10. Welcome title at Fernuni Schweiz for the participants of the SwissRN Computational Reproducibility Hackathon 2025.

September 2025:

- Organized a Mini Data Reproducibility Hackathon (September 6, Swiss Psychological Society Conference, Crans-Montana)
- Obtained funding from swissuniversities for Project “Open Online Course on Good Research Practices” Jointly with UZH-CRS, HES-SO VS, HEG-FR / HES-SO FR

Haute Ecole Spécialisée de Suisse occidentale (HES-SO)

Local Node representative: Grigorios Anagnostopoulos

- Meetings and educational activities via the community Open Science HES-SO (COS)
- Hosted webinars “Open data lunch HES-SO”
- Published scientific papers focused of the use of ORD for reproducibility
- Conducting the ROAD-TRIPIN project: Reinforcing Openly Accessible Data for Transparency and Reproducibility in Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation research

St. Gallen University of Teacher Education

Local Node representative: Michael Beck

January 2025:

- Founding of internal Data Steward Network

February 2025:

Love Data Week:

- Foster Replications and Secondary Data use in bachelor and master thesis'
- “One Dataset - Many Analysts”-Challenge

December 2025:

- Workshop on Data Archiving and Reuse in the Educational Sciences

University of Basel

Local Node representatives: Claudia Weidensteiner, Paul Ritsche

Throughout 2025:

- Organized the Basel ReproducibiliTEA club
- Hosted a talk by Prof. Anne Scheel
- University course: seminar series “Open Science: Principles and Practices for Better Research”

Open Science, Open Access & Research Data Management

Open Science, as an integral part of good scientific practice, promotes transparency in everyday research and thus provides an important building block for high-quality research. Furthermore, it enables optimal dissemination and visibility of the research results produced by members of the University of Basel, thereby improving their use for society.

Figure 11. University of Basel seminar series website on Open Science – screenshot.

January 2025:

- Organization of a kickoff meeting for the new Basel Reproducibility Network, The local Basel node is now a recognized Research Network within the University of Basel.

February 2025:

- Participated to “Love data week”

Figure 12. Love Data Week post banners at University of Basel – screenshot.

December 2025:

- Local organization of “SwissRN 4th Annual Meeting”

Figure 13. SwissRN Annual Meeting in Basel.

University of Bern

Local Node representative: Bernhard Voelkl

January 2025:

- Organization of the local node Bern meeting

October – November 2025:

- Development of a Reproducibility Module for the Graduate Schools
- Hosted the STRANGE Symposium (7 invited speakers, 62 participants) – Theme: “How sampling biases affect reproducibility of animal studies”.

Figure 14. STRANGE Symposium in Bern.

December 2025:

- Organized the Repro Seminar at the Institute for Space Research and Planetary Science
- Hosted the ReproducibiliTEA talk by Berna Devezer
- Offered a Reproducibility Module for the Graduate Schools GHS (Graduate School Health Sciences), GCB (Graduate School Cellular and Biomedical Sciences)

University of Geneva

Local Node representatives: Evie Vergauwe, Valentina Borghesani

Throughout 2025:

- Organized 6 ReproducibiliTea events: talks, papers, games

Figure 15. ReproducibiliTEA at University of Geneva including games.

February 2025:

- Conducted the SwissUbase Workshop

May 2025:

- Hosted a talk by Prof. Anne Scheel

November 2025:

Hosted the Reproducibility Day 2025, which included the following:

- Talk on preregistration by Dr. Malte Elson
- Presentation by local UNIGE services (e.g. library, ORD, ...)
- Hands-on workshop “Reproducible Research Workflows with Quarto and R - Getting Started”, led by instructors from CRS UZH and Academy

University of Zurich

Local Node representatives: Fabio Molo, Leonhard Held

November 2025:

- Organized the Workshop “Workflows with Quarto and R — Getting Started”
- Created a Open Educational Resources catalogue within the project “Open Online Course on Good Research Practices” jointly obtained with FernUni Schweiz
- Conducted research on reproducibility: e.g., [link to publication](#), [link to ongoing project](#)
- Organizing the [Research on Research Event](#) (taking place on 29–30 January 2026)

**REPRODUCIBILITY DAY 2025 @ UNIGE !
NOVEMBER 14TH @ UNI DUFOUR 408**

Join us for talks about reproducible research, learn about relevant UNIGE services, and get hands-on experience via a workshop on reproducible workflows in Quarto!

The morning session (open to all!) includes:

- **Presentations** of Open Science clubs and the SwissRN
- **Talk + Q&A** with Prof. Malte Elson (University of Bern)
- Information about available **UNIGE services**
- Light Lunch

The afternoon session (hybrid, in-person spots limited!) includes:

- **“Reproducible Research Workflows with Quarto and R - Getting Started” Workshop** with instructors from the Center for Reproducible Science of the University of Zurich

The morning session is open to everyone (no registration required), but the afternoon workshop requires registration (first come, first serve for in-person spots): Scan the QR above to register!

RN
CH Swiss Reproducibility Network

please contact reproducibilitea@unige.ch with any questions

FONDS GÉNÉRAL
DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE GENÈVE

Figure 16. Reproducible research workflows workshop in Geneva held by the CRS.

3. SwissRN 2025: Networking Milestone and Funding Sources

SwissRN 4th Annual Meeting

A key milestone for SwissRN at the national level was the successful organization of its 4th Annual Meeting. In 2025 the University of Basel local node of the SwissRN organized the 4th Annual Meeting, bringing together all local nodes and working groups to present their activities and highlight how SwissRN can support their efforts. The event provided a platform for exchange and coordination across the network, clarifying priorities and identifying areas for further development. It was held in a hybrid format and attracted more than 120 participants. In addition, representatives from four reproducibility networks (the Italian, French, Dutch, and German RNs) joined the meeting to explore opportunities for synergies and to align on strategies for advancing cultural change in support of open science and reproducibility at the international level.

The Annual Meeting featured a plenary talk by Katrin Milzow (Co-Director of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) on the SNSF's commitment to scientific reproducibility, followed by a panel discussion on the global development of reproducibility with contributions from invited speakers and the international RN representatives. Additional invited talks by Prof. Anne Scheel, an expert in reproducible research practices, and Silke Bellanger, an expert in open science and research data management, addressed challenges in rewarding reproducibility and strengthening data stewardship.

Funding Sources

SwissRN receives continued support by the **SNSF** for coordination and communication activities. This support contributes to the network's national-level activities, as SwissRN actively fosters cohesion and synergies across local nodes to strengthen the network as a whole. In addition, each of the network's local nodes receives in-kind and/or financial support directly from their host institutions. This support enables the nodes to carry out essential research, coordination, and outreach

activities, ensuring that they can actively contribute to the network’s overall objectives and impact at the national level.

In 2025, SwissRN also secured external funding from swissuniversities to support two projects:

“Participation in the Global Federation of Reproducibility Networks” project, awarded in Dec 2025 (planned start: 1st April 2026 with coordinator Barbara Templ). This project is led by the Center for Reproducible Science and Research Synthesis (CRS) at the University of Zurich to host the Global Federation of Reproducibility Networks (GFRN) Coordinating Office in 2026. This funding will ensure the operational stability of the GFRN, strengthen SwissRN’s role as a trusted partner in promoting transparent and responsible research practices, and enhance Switzerland’s leadership and integration in the international open science landscape.

swissuniversities

The “Open Online Course on Good Research Practices” project, awarded in July 2025, (see page xyz) has received funding to further establish and promote good research practices in connection with Open Science. The participating universities are: FernUni Schweiz, University of Zurich, Haute Ecole spécialisée de Suisse occidentale Valais/Wallis, and Haute école de Gestion, and Haute Ecole spécialisée de Suisse occidentale Fribourg. The main objective of this project is to develop and disseminate an open online course, including videos and podcasts, on best practices in Open Science, primarily targeting early career researchers while remaining accessible to the wider research community. The project will first set up an online learning platform to deliver high-quality educational content at a national level, with the platform designed for long-term use to host materials on Good Research Practices beyond Open Science. The initiative aims to connect with existing grassroots Open Science movements in Switzerland and internationally, creating resources that can support higher education institutions both nationally and abroad.

4. Conclusion and Outlook

Over the past year, our activities have continued to strengthen connections across the SwissRN community, fostering exchange, collaboration, and the dissemination of best practices. Through seminars, workshops, and initiatives such as ReproducibiliTea sessions, we have contributed to a growing culture of transparency and methodological rigor. At the same time, increasing visibility, particularly through digital channels such as LinkedIn and our newsletters, remains an important priority for amplifying impact and engagement.

Looking ahead, we aim to build on this momentum by expanding collaborative formats, including joint training sessions across institutions. A central goal is to translate practical insights into sustainable outputs, including best practice publications and the development of training opportunities in reproducibility. We will continue to support national initiatives, strengthen existing networks, contribute to collaborative funding discussions, and promote participation in key events.

In 2026, SwissRN will further expand its international impact by taking a leading role in coordinating the Global Federation of Reproducibility Networks (GFRN), while continuing to advocate for sustained support of Open Science initiatives. Strengthening ties with national and international partners will remain essential, even as resource constraints require careful prioritization.

Despite ongoing reliance on largely voluntary contributions and uncertain funding prospects, the commitment of our community remains strong. By consolidating our activities and sharing proven formats, we aim to further embed RTR research practices across the Swiss research landscape, while maintaining constructive exchanges with other national Reproducibility Networks in pursuit of this goal.